

TABLE 1

Complex CoCl ₂ with :	log K			Corresponding ΔF KCal/mole		
	Job's Curve	Yoe Jones's curve				
Cinchonine	7.67	8.36	8.65	-10.58	-11.61	-12.00
Quinine	8.47	8.03	8.38	-11.71	-11.14	-11.63

TABLE 2

Molecular formula	Percentage	Co	Cl	N	H ₂ O
C ₁₉ H ₂₂ ON ₂ .CoCl ₂ .H ₂ O (Cinchonine)	Found	12.60	16.12	5.82	3.23
	Required	13.35	16.04	6.34	4.07
C ₂₀ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₂ .CoCl ₂ .H ₂ O (Quinine)	Found	11.91	15.09	5.08	4.23
	Required	12.49	15.03	5.93	3.81

are capable of donation, the structure (I) may be assigned to cobalt chloride-cinchonine (R = H) and cobalt chloride-quinine (R = OCH₃) complexes. The structure (I) involves 7 and 8 membered rings which are not unlikely¹⁰ in coordination chemistry.

Structure (I) gets support from the fact that in the I.R. spectra of these complexes, metal-nitrogen absorption band is observed at 645 cm⁻¹ in cobalt chloride-quinine complex and metal-oxygen absorption bands are observed at 680 cm⁻¹ in both the complexes similar to Co-acetyl acetate. Further, absorption bands at 820, 3100 and 3500 cm⁻¹ in these complexes indicate co-ordinated water molecule.

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Manganese(III) Complexes with Aryl Schiff Bases

M. M. PATEL* & RATILAL P. PATEL

Department of Chemistry, Sardar Patel University, Vallabh Vidyanagar-388120

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RECENTLY Schiff bases with more than one coordinating centres have been used to stabilise manganese(III) ion¹⁻⁹. In continuation of our work on manganese(III) complexes¹⁰, we report now the

* Address : all correspondence to this author.

NOTES

results on manganese(III) complexes of ligands of the type I, where R = C₆H₅, C₆H₄CH₃(*m*) or C₆H₄Cl(*p*) and X = H or Br.

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Experimental

Manganese(III) acetate dihydrate was prepared as described previously¹⁰. 5-Br-salicylaldehyde was prepared by bromination, the recrystallised product from methanol melted at 140°. Toluidine and chloroaniline(*p*) were purified by distillation. Other solvents and chemicals were purified as described earlier¹⁰. The Schiff bases were prepared by warming equimolar quantities of amine and aldehyde in methanol on a water bath; the products were purified by recrystallisation from methanol (Sal.NC₆H₄CH₃(*m*), m.p. 41°; 5-Br-Sal-NC₆H₅, m.p. 118°; 5-Br-Sal-NC₆H₄Cl(*p*), m.p. 155°). The molar conductances of the complexes were determined using Konduktoskop, type E 365; reflectance spectra were recorded on Beckman DU by attaching standard reflectance attachment, lithium fluoride was used as reference and diluent material (samples were diluted about ten times). Electronic spectra in acetonitrile and magnetic moments were measured as described earlier¹⁰. The IR spectra were recorded in nujol mulls between sodium chloride plates on IR-5.

Preparation of the complexes :

Mn(Sal.NC₆H₄CH₃(*m*))₃: The solution of the ligand, 5-Br-Sal.NC₆H₄CH₃(*m*) (0.015 mole) in methanolic KOH was warmed on water bath and filtered and to the filtrate, manganese(III) acetate dihydrate (0.005 mole) was added. The solution on stirring gave olive green product which was filtered off and washed with ice cold methanol and dried in a vacuum desiccator over CaCl₂.

Olive green complexes, Mn(5-Br-Sal.NC₆H₅)₃ and Mn(5-Br-Sal.NC₆H₄Cl(*p*))₃ were also prepared, washed and dried as described above. Manganese was estimated as described earlier¹⁰. Nitrogen was estimated by Dumas' method for the complexes Mn(5-Br-Sal.NC₆H₄Cl(*p*))₃ and Mn(5-Br-Sal.NC₆H₅)₃ while for Mn(Sal.NC₆H₄CH₃(*m*))₃ Kjeldahl's method was used.

Results and Discussion

The magnetic moments of the complexes are close to the value of 4.90 B.M. expected for spin-free manganese(III) complexes with four unpaired electrons.

The molar conductances of the complexes in acetonitrile and methanol, in the concentration of about 3.0-6.0 × 10⁻⁴M are in the range of 1.3-3.5 and 17.8-38.4 mhos respectively. The conductance values show that the complexes dissociate very little in acetonitrile while they undergo considerable dissociation in methanol. In both the solvents, complexes behave as non-electrolytes⁴.

A strong band found around 1628 cm⁻¹ in the IR spectra (Table 1) of the ligands is attributed to the C = N stretch¹¹⁻¹³. This band is shifted towards lower frequency in complexes which is an indication of the coordination of the Schiff bases through the azomethine nitrogen¹¹. The strong band found around 1285 cm⁻¹ in the ligands is assigned to the phenolic C-O stretching vibrations^{11,14}. This band is shifted towards higher frequency on complexation indicating that *o*-hydroxy group of the Schiff base has taken part in complex formation.

Usually the spin-free manganese(III) complexes with octahedral geometry, are expected to give one *d-d* transition¹⁵, ⁶E_g → ⁵T_{2g} around 20,000 cm⁻¹. In the complexes studied here, one intense and sharp band around 25,000 cm⁻¹ (in acetonitrile) and other relatively less intense and broad band around 15,000 cm⁻¹ (in acetonitrile and reflectance) are observed. The band around 25,000 cm⁻¹ is assigned to a charge transfer^{3,6,16}. The band around 15,000 cm⁻¹ is assignable to *d-d* transition^{4,6}. The broadening of this band may suggest that complexes have

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS OF THE COMPLEXES, AND IR BANDS (CM⁻¹) OF THE SCHIFF BASES AND THEIR COMPLEXES

Complex	Calc. %		Found %		μ_{eff} (B.M.)	$\nu_{C=N}$	ν_{C-O}
	Mn	N	Mn	N			
Mn(Sal.NC ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (<i>m</i>)) ₃	7.98	6.13	8.10	6.11	4.97	1613 (1631)	1312 (1290)
Mn(5-Br-Sal.NC ₆ H ₅) ₃	6.22	4.75	6.31	4.50	5.03	1618 (1626)	1300 (1282)
Mn(5-Br-Sal.NC ₆ H ₄ Cl(<i>p</i>)) ₃	5.58	4.26	5.49	4.24	4.84	1618 (1626)	1296 (1282)

more than one $d-d$ transition, indicating distortion from octahedral symmetry^{4,6}.

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Stability Constants and Thermodynamic Functions of Aspartic Acid Chelates of Pr(III) and Gd(III) Ions

R. C. AGARWAL

Department of Chemistry, Bipin Bihari College,
Jhansi-284001

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accepted 9 April 1974

THE complexes of aspartic acid with metal ions like Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cr^{3+} have been reported in literature by many workers^{1,2}. Batyaev *et al.*³ have reported the stability constants of complexes of aspartic acid with La^{3+} , Ce^{3+} , Pr^{3+} and Nd^{3+} at 25°. Trivedi and Sunar⁴ have reported thermodynamic functions of aspartic acid chelates of Nd^{3+} and Sm^{3+} recently. The present work is intended to study the stabilities of complexes of aspartic acid

with Pr^{3+} and Gd^{3+} ions at different temperatures and determine overall changes in free energy, enthalpy and entropy. In this paper the stability constant of Pr^{3+} as given by Batyaev *et al.* is verified with the addition of the thermodynamic functions.

Experimental

Pr and Gd oxides were dissolved in the calculated amount of perchloric acid. The metal content of the solutions were gravimatically estimated, by precipitating as oxalate and then igniting as oxide. Other solutions were prepared in conductivity water. NaClO_4 was used to adjust the ionic strength. All the chemicals used were of A.R. (B.D.H. or equivalent) quality.

The constant temperature water was circulated through the titration vessel made of pyrex glass, from thermostat, where the temperature was controlled within 0.1°. The experimental procedure involved a series of pH titrations of aspartic acid with standard NaOH solution in the absence of and in presence of metal ions at different temperatures 35°, 45° and 55°. The sets for different pH titrations were made according to author's another paper under communication⁵. In all the titrations the volume (25 ml) and ionic strength (0.1M NaClO_4) were kept constant.

Curve A : Only for aspartic acid for both the experiments.
Curves B, C, D : For aspartic acid and Pr(III) at 35°, 45° and 55°.
Curves B', C', D' : For aspartic acid and Gd(III) at 35°, 45° and 55°.

Results and Discussions

The pH value of the systems B, C, D and B', C', D' is lower than the corresponding value in A indicating the liberation of proton due to complex formation.

